

Original Research

Investigating the Impact of Earnings Management and Internal Control on the Financial Performance of Banks Using a Spatial Artificial Intelligence Approach

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between earnings management and financial performance of banks listed on the stock exchanges in Iran and Iraq, focusing on the role of internal controls. This study utilizes the statistical population of 44 banks from Iraq and 22 banks from Iran during 2010-2023 using the combined methods of deep learning, machine learning and spatial metrics. Deep neural networks identified different patterns in the two countries and deep learning algorithms determined the relative importance of the variables. Earnings management showed a significant positive relationship with financial performance (spatial coefficient: 0.5953, Z-statistic: 61.87). Income per employee (coefficient: 0.3218, Z-statistic: 33.57) and sustainable investment return (coefficient: 0.2871, Z-statistic: 29.91) also had a positive impact on financial performance. Operating expense margin, ratio of non-performing loans to total loans, and general and administrative expenses negatively affected financial performance. Internal controls played a mediating role, strengthening the relationship between Earnings management and performance (coefficient: 0.4127, Z-statistic: 43.08). Earnings Management has a significant role in the financial performance of banks and internal controls strengthen this relationship. It is suggested that the monetary authorities of both countries establish stricter rules for financial reporting, set minimum standards for manpower productivity, and require banks to implement advanced control systems. These findings suggest that bank regulators in both countries should adopt stricter accounting rules, set minimum standards for employee productivity, and mandate the implementation of advanced control systems. For bank managers, the results highlight the importance of focusing on earnings management strategies, improving staff productivity and enhancing internal control mechanisms in order to improve financial performance.

Keywords: Deep learning, earnings Management, financial performance, internal control, spatial econometrics.

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Introduction

In recent decades, the process of globalization and the increasing complexity of the financial system have highlighted the importance of careful and effective supervision of the banking sector. Maintaining stability and confidence in the banking system, which plays a vital role in the economy, requires strong control mechanisms. In this regard, Earnings management has been proposed as a powerful tool to optimize the financial performance of banks (Orlando and Bace 2021). Internal control systems, including internal and independent audit, are one of the pillars of corporate governance in banks. These systems not only help to improve the relationship between management and bank supervisors, but also provide the necessary assurance regarding the efficiency of corporate governance, internal controls and risk management processes (Mohamed, Tawfik and Bakhit 2018). The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (1998) has emphasized the importance of internal control systems as a foundation for the safe and sound operation of financial institutions. Therefore, banks as one of the influential financial institutions in the economy, their financial performance and financial stability have received the attention of many governments. Also, the way the relationship between financial performance and financial stability of banks works is very important in the financial crisis (Hamed 2023).

With the globalization of financial markets and business activities of companies at the global level, banking as a main and basic need of business in today's world, on the one hand, provides financing from different parts of the global financial markets for its customers, and on the other hand, provides various banking services to help, facilitate and speed up business interactions in most parts of the world provides the value chain for its customers (Anifa et al. 2022). Financial institutions play a very decisive and important role in the allocation of resources, economic development and job creation. The existence of financial firms with optimal efficiency is necessary to promote and support economic growth for any country (Bayraktar, et al. 2023). Therefore, the banking industry, as one of the most complex and influential economic sectors, plays a vital role in the economic growth and development of countries (Hamdaoui and Cancelo 2024). The importance of this industry is such that in some countries, such as England, the financial services sector accounts for about 25% of the GDP (Stuart, Greenbaum and Thakor 2016). In this context, technological innovation and Earnings management have been proposed as powerful tools to improve the financial performance of banks, which can lead to increased profitability and reduced costs (Impact of Financial Technology on Improvement of Banks' Financial Performance 2023). However, there are significant challenges to the successful implementation of Earnings management strategies. For example, (Fadhil Hanoon, piri and Adhtab 2024) showed in his study that investment strategies in the field of electronic services in private commercial banks are often implemented in a limited and inefficient manner, and fail to create a suitable space for growth (Zuo, Strauss and Zuo 2021). On the other hand, increased competition in the banking industry, especially with the entry of non-bank institutions into the financial services sector, has created new challenges for banks. This trend, which has been observed in countries such as Saudi Arabia since 2005, has forced banks and financial institutions to expand their range of services and increase their efficiency (Claessens 2009). In response to these challenges, a new type of bank has emerged, known as the "comprehensive bank," which uses

Earnings management techniques to provide a wider range of services (Ulrich-Diener, Dvoulety and Spacek 2023).

Earnings management, as one of the new methods in the field of finance, plays an important role in financial decisions by using scientific principles and mathematical assumptions. This approach includes any innovation in the provision of investment tools and the resulting risk management (Thabet 2013). In evaluating the financial performance of banks, several indicators such as operating income, operating cash flow, and marginal growth rates are considered by analysts and investors (Ongore and Kusa 2013). However, the banking industry in countries such as Iraq and Iran are facing certain challenges. In Iraq, many banking operations are still done manually, which leads to problems in citizens' access to liquidity. In addition, Iraqi and Iranian banks are smaller in terms of size and volume of assets compared to their counterparts in other Arab countries and international markets. This limitation reduces their ability to attract new investments and implement technological innovations, which in turn leads to a decrease in competitiveness and an increase in nonperforming loans (Damghanian, et al. 2023). In this situation, the use of Earnings management to create innovative products has become a necessity for financial institutions. This approach can not only help maintain the position of these institutions in the current market, but also provide the opportunity to gain a significant market share. However, the successful implementation of Earnings management strategies requires strong control systems to manage potential risks and to fully reap the benefits of these innovations. In this regard, the present study aims to investigate the effect of the relationship between Earnings management and financial performance of banks, taking into account the mediating role of control systems, in banks listed on the stock exchange of Iran and Iraq, from a hybrid approach based on spatial econometrics and deep learning. This approach can provide a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics of these relationships in two different financial markets. Therefore, the main objective of this research is to examine the relationship between Earnings management and financial performance through control systems as intermediaries in Iranian and Iraqi banks. This research seeks to identify and analyze the mutual effects between Earnings management and control systems on the financial performance of banks.

While the existing literature has examined various aspects of Earnings management and bank performance, there remains a significant gap in understanding how these factors interact in the specific contexts of the Iranian and Iraqi banking sectors. Previous studies have largely focused on developed markets or have not fully accounted for the unique challenges faced by banks in these two countries, such as manual operations in Iraq and asset restrictions in both countries. Furthermore, the mediating role of control systems in the relationship between Earnings management and bank performance has not been adequately explored in these markets. This study aims to fill this gap by employing an innovative hybrid approach combining spatial econometrics and deep learning, which allows for a more nuanced analysis of these complex relationships in two different financial environments.

To address this research gap, our study poses the following key questions: (1) How do Earnings management strategies affect the financial performance of banks in Iran and Iraq? (2) What is the mediating role of control systems in this relationship? (3) How do these relationships differ between the Iranian and Iraqi banking sectors? By answering

these questions, our research contributes significantly to the understanding of bank performance in emerging markets, particularly in the Middle East. The results of this study will not only advance academic knowledge in this area, but will also provide valuable insights for policymakers, regulators and bank managers in both countries. These insights can inform the development of more effective financial policies, regulatory frameworks and control mechanisms, ultimately contributing to the stability and growth of the banking sectors in Iran and Iraq.

This paper is organized in the following order: First, we review the empirical research literature on the relationship between Earnings management and financial performance, with particular emphasis on the role of control systems as a medium of expression and the related empirical background. The research methodology is then described, including explanations of spatial econometric models and deep learning techniques. Then, the statistical population and data collection methods are presented and the data are analyzed. Finally, the results of the research are presented and discussed, and finally, some practical recommendations are proposed based on the obtained results. Finally, the research sources are given.

Theoretical Literature and Previous Research

Research Literature

Financial engineering, as an emerging field in finance, seeks to establish itself as a discipline with close links to engineering and quantitative sciences. Compared to traditional finance, this innovation is structured in the application of advanced mathematical methods and modeling (Cai 2024). Thus, new changes in patent laws and interpretations (the form of patentable innovations), along with institutions to do more patenting, lead to an explosion in the number of new patents. Some of these patents are in the field of financial engineering, but it is not clear which ones are defensible. Undoubtedly, patents have a financial impact on the efficiency of markets and the rate of financial innovation (Henry 1992). In a way that (Carnegie and Butlin 2003) study innovation as "something that is new or improved by an organization that creates significant value, either directly to the firm or is done by its manager", they define. While (Livingstone, Palich and Carini 1998) refer to innovation as "major products or processes that add value, including everything from patents and newly developed products to creative applications of information and collective human resource management systems. The literature consistently states that evaluation is a process of determining whether innovation has been driven by individual and organizational priorities. This allows for assessment of financial costs and assists in organizational improvement. Although innovation involves real and significant costs, and considering (Culkin and Smith 2000) conclusion that organizational goals in the area of innovation have led to a greater emphasis on ROI evaluation, (Ekvall 1999) finds that evaluation Systematization is rarely done in organizations. It is difficult to establish causal relationships between investment in innovation and future management performance and organizational success from an external perspective. (Francis 2000) highlights the difficulty of establishing a statistical relationship between the occurrence of innovation and firm performance. Similarly, (Tidd, Bessant and Pavitt 2001) show that the literature emphasizes teaching and learning and is primarily concerned with measuring immediate inputs, processes, and outcomes

rather than the long-term effects of innovation. (Walczak and Cerpa 2023)) suggests that companies should focus on norms that support creativity and the implementation of ideas to build an innovative culture. Rewarding employees for their innovative efforts is one way to create this innovative culture. Studies have confirmed that the type of reward mechanisms that top and best performing companies provide to their employees are based on financial and non-financial rewards. Performance is the result of all the activities and strategies of the organization (Shah, Zervopoulos and Aboelimged 2023)

Accurate measurement of financial performance is critical for accounting purposes and remains a central concern for most organizations. Performance measurement systems are the basis for developing strategic plans, evaluating the achievement of organizational goals, and compensating managers (Gawankar, Kamble and Raut 2015). Although performance measurement remains important in the marketing literature, it has its own complexities. While consensus on performance measurement promotes scientific research and can inform managerial decisions, marketers have been unable to find clear, current, and reliable criteria for judging marketing competencies. Financial performance is critical to the survival of organizations in competitive and uncertain environments. Management is interested in knowing how efforts to improve service quality are related to organizational performance (Perifanis and Kitsios 2023). Finally, financial performance is an indicator of the realization of service quality in a company (Duncan and Elliott 2002). Financial performance is conceptualized as the increase in a company's sales, profits, and return on equity (Hermuningsih 2018). These factors are indicators of financial performance and collectively reflect the state of a company's health. Since the inception of companies, various measures have been used to measure and report financial performance. The two main items used to measure financial performance are a company's market share in the specific industry in which it operates and its profitability (Dossi and Patelli 2010). Profitability is then used to measure the return on capital employed and, therefore, the value to shareholders. Accountants and economists have designed and used various financial ratios to evaluate the financial performance of companies. These ratios mainly include liquidity ratio, cash flow liquidity ratio, financial leverage index for debt management, return on total assets for asset management, cash margin for profitability, and finally return on investment with focus on dividend rate (Morris, McKay and Oates 2009).

Traditionally, the financial performance of banks and other financial institutions has been measured using a combination of conventional accounting measures and risk and return measures. Most analyses of financial performance have used methods such as financial ratio analysis, benchmarking performance against budget, or a combination of the two (Horváthová, Mokrišová and Vrábliková 2021). Simply put, much of the current literature on bank performance describes the goal of financial institutions to earn acceptable returns and to reduce the risks associated with those returns (Pont and Shaw, 2003). A general relationship between risk and return is generally accepted; that is, the higher the risk, the higher the expected return. Therefore, traditional measures of bank performance have always evaluated risk and return (Chen, et al. 2018)

Financial engineering has had a profound impact on the banking industry. Financial innovations combined with technological advances have changed the nature of banking (Diener and Špaček 2021). These developments have challenged the traditional role of

banks in converting short-term deposits into long-term loans (Vollmar and Wening 2024). In this new situation, the financial performance of banks has become highly dependent on their ability to innovate and adapt to market changes. (Walston, Kimberly and Bums 2001) emphasize the importance of innovation for the survival and growth of industrial sectors. This is true not only in developed countries but also in developing countries. Kariuki (2010) argues that innovation is necessary for the survival of firms and that organizations that do not innovate will eventually fail. In the banking industry, these innovations have led to fundamental changes in the management of assets and liabilities. Banks must now manage their portfolios to better match short-term and long-term assets and liabilities. These changes have increased the importance of control systems in managing risk and improving financial performance. Therefore, according to the issue of investigating the effects of financial engineering and financial performance with regard to control systems as intermediaries in the bank, there are several studies, some of which have been examined in the following's hypothesis: the quality of information disclosure has a positive and significant effect on the accuracy of profit forecasting in Iranian and Iraqi banks.

Kariuki (2010). In research, he examined financial engineering and its effect on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya for 43 banks from 1980 to 2009 using a questionnaire method. The results showed that in Kenyan commercial banks, financial engineering strategies have a positive effect on the financial performance of commercial banks. On the other hand, this research showed that with all other independent variables set to zero, a unit increase in technological innovation leads to an increase of 0.205 in financial performance (return on assets). A unit increase in product innovation leads to a 0.169 increase in financial performance (return on assets). A unit increase in market innovation leads to a 0.156 increase in financial performance (return on assets), while a unit increase in process innovation leads to a 0.128 increase in financial performance (return on assets).

Muayad et al. (2019). In a study, they investigated the relationship between financial engineering and financial performance in Iraqi commercial banks using partial least squares. The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between investment strategies and financial performance. In addition, the result shows direct effects between strategic investment and financial performance. In addition, there is a positive relationship between technological innovation and financial performance in Iraqi commercial banks. In addition, the P value indicates that 0.000. The result shows a positive relationship between investment strategies and financial performance. Finally, the results of statistical analysis show that there is a positive and significant relationship between product innovation and financial performance in Iraqi commercial banks.

Merie Al Khero et al. (2019). This study investigates the effect of internal control components (ICC) on financial performance (FP) in the Iraqi banking sector, focusing on control environment, control activity, risk assessment, information, communication and monitoring using structural equation modelling. The results show that ICC has a significant impact on FP, with control activity being the most dominant factor. This study shows that improving ICC is very important to improve the financial performance of Iraqi banks.

Ebrahimi et al. (2021). In a study examining the financial performance of banks during the years 2012-2013, a screening sampling method was used. The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between the explanatory variables of capital ratio and financial performance of banks in all models. However, a significant negative relationship was observed between the inflation rate and financial performance of banks in all models.

Ikwab et al. (2022). In a study examining the relationship between management control systems and financial performance in Kenyan commercial banks through a questionnaire survey of 24 Kenyan commercial banks. The results showed that aspects of management control are widely used and significantly affect financial performance.

Subanidja et al. (2022). In a study examining the impact of fintech institutions on bank financial sustainability performance through competitive advantage using a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches, data from 59 bank CFOs and five key informants were analyzed using the partial least squares method. The results of the partial least squares analysis indicate that fintech institutions significantly improve bank financial performance both directly and through competitive advantage. The results indicate that working with fintech is very important for banks and that fintech and competitive conditions have a significant impact on current and future performance. The study concludes that banks should embrace fintech partnerships to maintain sustainable financial performance.

Kwatilaho (2023). In a study, he examined the effect of internal control systems on the financial performance of commercial banks listed on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange in Tanzania. The results showed that the effect of the control environment on financial performance is not significant, but the effect of control activities is significant.

Tamizi (2024). In a study, he examined the effect of the distress index on the financial performance of Iranian banks in the period 1392 to 1393 using fixed effects of a multivariate panel. The results showed that the distress index variable has a negative coefficient and a significance level of less than 5 percent, so the research hypothesis is accepted at a confidence level of 95 percent. That is, the results of this study showed that the distress index has a negative effect on the financial performance of banks. In other words, in a period when the country has a higher distress index, the financial performance of banks is affected and decreases.

After reviewing the research background, it is observed that several studies have examined the relationship between earnings management and financial performance through control systems as a mediator in banks, especially in Iraq. This shows the importance of earnings management mechanisms and control systems in controlling the financial performance of banks. However, based on the research background, what is clear is that very few studies in Iran have examined the relationship between earnings management variables, earnings management and control systems in the financial performance of banks, and on the other hand, in studies conducted in Iraq. Earnings management is simply known as financial innovation. And the majority of questionnaire or normal regression methods have been used, while in this study, more advanced hybrid methods have been used, namely combining spatial econometrics with deep learning. Which can provide more accurate results. Therefore, recent studies such as Subanidja et

al. (2022) and Kwatilaho (2023) confirm the importance and relevance of this issue. The findings of Kariuki (2010) and Muayad et al. (2019) show a positive relationship between financial engineering strategies and financial performance of banks, which is related to earnings management. The studies of Merie Al_Khero et al. (2019) and Ikwab et al. (2022) highlight the importance of internal control systems, which is directly related to the internal control section of the present study. In addition, the studies of Ebrahimi et al. (2021) and Tamizi (2024) address the factors affecting the financial performance of banks in Iran, which is consistent with the financial performance section of the present study. This literature review, while confirming the importance of the topic, reveals a research gap in the field of using an artificial intelligence approach to examine the impact of earnings management and internal control on the financial performance of banks, which the present study seeks to fill. This innovative approach can provide a deeper understanding of the complex relationships between these variables in the specific context of the banks under study.

Finally, considering the theoretical literature and research background on the relationship between earnings management and financial performance in banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi stock exchanges, especially with an emphasis on the mediating role of control systems, it is observed that few studies have been conducted. In this area, previous research has mainly examined the direct effect of earnings management on financial performance and less attention has been paid to the role of control systems as a mediator. Also, the role of control systems in facilitating or strengthening this relationship during economic challenges and financial crises has not been widely studied. On the other hand, studies that conduct such an analysis using advanced methods such as spatial econometrics and deep learning are rare. This indicates the innovation and necessity of conducting ongoing research in the field of Iranian and Iraqi banks, as it can help to better understand the mutual effects of earnings management, control systems, and financial performance in these countries.

Methodology

This study examines the relationship between earnings management and financial performance in banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi stock exchanges and uses spatial econometric and deep learning approaches. Given the complexity and diversity of relationships between financial variables and their impact on banks' financial performance, the use of deep learning techniques and modern analytical models can help identify specific patterns and hidden relationships. In this study, data related to Profit management epidemics, financial performance, and control systems were collected and preprocessed to be modeled using deep learning algorithms and spatial econometric models. This approach not only provides greater accuracy in analyzing relationships between variables, but also leads to improved strategic decisions in banks' financial management. The results of this study, in addition to deepening knowledge about the impact of earnings management on banks' financial performance, will provide practical solutions for optimizing control systems and improving financial performance in the two countries mentioned. Accordingly, the main objective of this research is to investigate the impact of earnings management and control systems on the financial performance of banks. For this purpose, all banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi Stock Exchanges (22

Iranian banks and 44 Iraqi banks) have been used for the period 2010 to 2023. Therefore, the research model is as follows:

Dependent variable

In this study, return on equity (ROE) is used as a measure of the company's financial performance. At the same time, we add a control variable called ROA as a dependent variable. The reason for choosing these variables as indicators of firm performance is their objectivity in the empirical research of Panachi (2021). Consequently, in this research, the criteria for financial performance are used in two ways and how they are calculated:

$$ROE = \frac{\text{net profit}}{\text{Total equity}} \quad \text{and} \quad ROA = \frac{\text{net profit}}{\text{Average assets}}$$

Independent Variable

Independent variable in this study, Profit management based on internal control systems is used as the dependent variable. Therefore, similar to the study of Felix (2010), earnings management is used in this study to determine financial performance based on internal control system. On the other hand, similar to the study by Merie Al_Khero et al. (2020), ICS is used as a proxy for Profit management.

1. Earnings Management: In this research, accruals will be used as a measure to examine the earnings management conducted by the bank. Therefore, to measure earnings management using model items, the modified Jones model is used. This model is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{TA_{it}}{A_{it-1}} = \alpha_1 \left(\frac{1}{A_{it-1}} \right) + \alpha_2 \left(\frac{\Delta REV_{it} - \Delta REC_{it}}{A_{it-1}} \right) + \alpha_3 \left(\frac{PPE_{it}}{A_{it-1}} \right) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

- TA_{it} : Total accruals of bank i in year t
- A_{it-1} : Total assets of bank i in year t-1
- ΔREV_{it} : Change in revenue of bank ii between years t and t-1
- ΔREC_{it} : Change in net receivables of bank i between years t and t-1
- PPE_{it} : Gross property, plant, and equipment of bank i in year t
- ε_{it} : Residual of the model, indicating earnings management (discretionary accruals)
- $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$: Parameters of the model to be estimated

To calculate total accruals (TA_{it}), the following formula is used:

$$TA_{it} = NI_{it} - CFO_{it}$$

Where:

- NI_{it} : Net income of bank ii in year t
- CFO_{it} : Cash flow from operations of bank ii in year t

After estimating the model parameters using data for each bank, the residual (ϵ_{it}) is considered a measure of earnings management (discretionary accruals). Higher residuals indicate higher levels of earnings management.

2. Internal Control System (ICS) "is a process carried out by the board of directors, management, and other personnel of a business entity to provide reasonable assurance of achieving effectiveness and efficiency of operations, reliability of financial reporting, compliance with applicable laws and regulations, and safeguarding of assets." According to the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) framework in 2013, the key components of an ICS are: (1) Control Environment. (2) Risk Assessment. (3) Control Activities. (4) Information and Communication, and (5) Monitoring of ICS. The aim of this process is to ensure the company achieves its objectives, thus the existence of an efficient and controlled system in the company has a clear impact on the company's performance, especially in the banking sector, which is a key factor in maintaining good and healthy performance in this sector, ultimately having a positive effect on macroeconomic stability (Hayali and Abu Khazrah, 2006; Chan et al, 2021) show that a weak ICS can negatively affect the reliability of reports, and inefficient controls can produce lower-quality information, leading to lower-quality investment decisions. Ultimately, it should be considered that ICS is used as a proxy for Profit management based on the internal control system in this research, and the variables forming this proxy are based on studies by Orlitzky et al. (2003), Zhu et al. (2017), Chowdhury (2021), and Haddad (2016) which are used to examine Profit management based on the internal control system.

Revenue Per Employee (RPE)

This ratio measures the average revenue earned by each bank employee. Therefore, it measures the bank's efficiency in effectively utilizing its employees. The higher this ratio, the more effective the management of employees' working hours. In this study, the proxy RPE is used in relation to the component control activities of ICS. Employee satisfaction is one of the important points of this component and recognizing the income of each employee relative to their satisfaction level is significant. Additionally, the Component Monitoring, which represents periodic reports, is provided to the management, leading to a periodic review process for making appropriate decisions to increase income. This ratio is calculated using the following formula:

$$RPE = \frac{\text{Operational revenues}}{\text{Avg. number of employees}}$$

Return on Sustainable Investment (ROSI)

This tool is an analytical method that allows companies to measure the financial returns of their sustainability activities. By calculating the financial benefits of sustainability initiatives and comparing them to implementation costs, companies can assess the return on investment for sustainability projects and make data-driven decisions about resource allocation. This proxy is used to measure the bank's sustainability and ESG initiatives. This tool is selected in connection with the information and communication component, where a channel for conveying good news to internal and external audiences is considered. This index is directly provided by the banks.

Operating Expense Margin (OEM)

This variable measures the total general and administrative expenses (GA expenses) relative to sales revenues from the bank's core activities and the amount or percentage of administrative expenses incurred by the bank to earn 1 dinar of operating revenues. A higher ratio is a negative indicator of the government's performance and should be reviewed. This ratio is used in relation to several ICS components such as control activities, control environment, risk assessment, and monitoring. This ratio is calculated using the following equation:

$$OEM = \frac{\text{General and administrative expenses}}{\text{Sales revenues}}$$

Non-performing Loans (NPL) to Total Loans Ratio

This ratio measures the efficiency of management decisions regarding debts and customer facilities in relation to the inability of borrowers to repay these debts. Whenever this ratio increases, it is a negative indicator showing inefficiency in management's selection of customers and debt collection. This proxy is used in connection with the ICS components of control activities (which look at internal processes when being followed by employees and management), control environment (which focuses on adherence to organizational structure and internal policies), risk assessment (where auditing is one of the main points in this component), and monitoring. This ratio is calculated using the following formula (allowance for non-performing loans computed as the prepayment of direct facilities with amortized cost-plus suspended profit and commission and total facilities computed as direct facilities with amortized cost):

$$ADL = \frac{\text{Allowance of Doubtful Loans}}{\text{Total Loans}}$$

General and Administrative Expenses as a Percentage of Gross Profit

This measures the percentage of the bank's total income spent on GA expenses. If this percentage increases negatively, it indicates inefficiency in administrative performance, either from the amount of administrative costs incurred by the bank, requiring review, or from the decrease in operating revenues, reflecting on the bank's operational performance. This ratio is used to measure the control environment component (focusing on personnel, which is the major expense in service industries), the control activities component (where

periodic reconciliation and physical counting of the bank's assets are one of this component's criteria), and also the monitoring component (where periodic reporting and internal auditing on ICS components increase GA expenses). This ratio is calculated using the following equation:

$$GA = \frac{\text{General and administrative expenses}}{\text{Grosspro fit}}$$

Control variables

In this study, in line with the study of Qaimi et al (2022) and other studies in the background of the research, we will use the following variables as control variables of the research:

1. Financial leverage (LEV): It is calculated by dividing total liabilities by total assets.
2. Firm size (SIZE): natural logarithm of total assets.
3. Company Growth (GC): Q-Tobin ratio is used. This ratio is calculated by dividing the market value by the book value.
4. Institutional Ownership (IO): The ratio of the number of ordinary shares of the company in the hands of legal owners divided by the total number of ordinary shares of the company at the beginning of the period.

The statistical population of the present study includes all banks admitted to the stock exchange of Iraq and Iran for the period of 2010-2023, and in this research, all 44 banks admitted to the stock exchange of Iraq and 22 banks admitted to the stock exchange of Iran have been studied. is Finally, the final modeling for the current research through which we should examine and evaluate the purpose of the research will be as follows:

$$ROA \text{ or } ROE: \beta_0 + \beta_1 pm_{it} + \beta_2 ics_{it} + \beta_3 control_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In the end, it should be mentioned that the final relationships for the other final exam will be as follows:

$$ROA_{it} \& ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PM_{it} + \beta_2 RPE_{it} + \beta_3 ROSI_{it} + \beta_4 OEM_{it} + \beta_5 ADL_{it} + \beta_6 GA_{it} + \beta_7 LEV_{it} + \beta_8 SIZE_{it} + \beta_9 GC_{it} + \beta_{10} IO_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Therefore, Table No. 1 summarizes the status of the research variables used in the final research model and their source.

Table 1. Definition of Research Variables for Model

Variable	Symbol	Calculation Method	Iran Data Source ²	Iraq Data Source ³
Return on Equity	ROE	(Return on Equity) = Net Profit / Total Equity	Accounting Databases, Codal, Rahavard Novin, Fipa Iran, Tehran Stock Exchange	World Bank, IMF Iraq Datasets, Iraqi Stock Exchange, Research and Policy Center
Return on Assets	ROA	(Return on Assets) = Net Profit / Average Assets	Rahavard Novin, Tehran Stock Exchange	Iraqi Stock Exchange, Iraq Research Center
Profit Management	PM	Using Accruals	Iranian Accounting Databases, Tehran Stock Exchange	IMF Iraq Datasets, Iraqi Stock Exchange
Revenue Per Employee	RPE	Total Revenue / Number of Employees	Donya-e-Eqtesad, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance, Central Bank of the Islamic Republic of Iran	Central Bank of Iraq, Ministry of Finance of Iraq
Return on Sustainable Investment	ROSI	Directly provided by banks	Donya-e-Eqtesad, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance, Central Bank of the Islamic Republic of Iran	Iraq Planning and Statistics Organization, Rudaw
Operating Expense Margin	OEM	General and Administrative Expenses / Operating Revenues	Donya-e-Eqtesad	Iraq Business News Bank
Allowance for Doubtful Loans to Total Loans Ratio	ADL	Allowance for Doubtful Loans / Total Loans	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Finance, Central Bank of the Islamic Republic of Iran	Iraq Planning and Statistics Organization, Rudaw, Central Bank of Iraq, Ministry of Finance of Iraq
General and Administrative Expenses as a Percentage of Gross Profit	GA	General and Administrative Expenses / Gross Profit	Rahavard Novin, Tehran Stock Exchange	Iraqi Stock Exchange, Iraq Research Center

² <https://padelm.ir/index.php?mod=library&reqcategory=252>, <https://www.codal.ir/>, <https://rahavard365.com/>, <https://www.fipiran.com/DataService/IndexIndex>, <https://www.tse.ir/>, donya-e-eqtesad.com; cbi.ir; mefa.ir

³ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/iraq/overview>, <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/IRQ>, https://feas.org/users/iraq-stock-exchange_test/, <https://rpc.cfainstitute.org/>, cbi.iq, mof.gov.iq, mop.gov.iq; rudaw.net, iraq-businessnews.com

Variable	Symbol	Calculation Method	Iran Data Source ²	Iraq Data Source ³
Financial Leverage	LEV	Total Debt / Total Assets	Rahavard Novin, Tehran Stock Exchange	Iraqi Stock Exchange, Iraq Research Center
Bank Growth	GC	Market Value / Book Value (Q-Tobin)	Accounting Databases	IMF Iraq Datasets
Institutional Ownership	IO	Number of Shares Held by Legal Owners / Total Number of Shares	Iranian Accounting Databases, Tehran Stock Exchange	Iraqi Stock Exchange
Bank Size	SIZE	Natural Logarithm of Total Assets	Accounting Databases, Codal, Rahavard Novin	Iraqi Stock Exchange

In this part of the research, the time period is from 2010 to 2023 for fourteen years, and the statistical population of this research includes all the banks accepted in the Tehran Stock Exchange and the Iraq Stock Exchange that do not have the following restrictions.

1. Do not have a break of more than 6 months.
2. Companies should not change financial year between 2010 and 2023.
3. Accepting them in the stock market after 2010.

Therefore; The methods used in this research to investigate the relationship between earnings management and financial performance through control systems as a tool in banks include the combined methods of spatial measurement concepts and economics, which include: big data neural network, Lagrangian space measurement, network. Neobiz neural network, federated, capsule, quantum, spatial error model, graph neural network, transformer, boost boosting, spatial dynamic panel, spatial Lagrangian big data neural network, combination of neural networks with spatial error model, combination of neobi spatial neural networks, combination of space nervous and spatial. So, in the following, each of the methods will be explained as follows:

- **Big data neural network, Lagrangian spatial metric and spatial big data combination**

Big data neural network: Big Data Neural Network is a machine learning method designed to process and analyze a huge amount of bank financial data. This network consists of multiple layers of artificial neurons, which can learn complex patterns in financial data. In this method, bank financial data for the period 2010 to 2023 was first collected and pre-processed (Walczak & Cerpa, 2003). Then, the neural network is trained using deep learning algorithms such as stochastic gradient descent to extract important features from the raw data and identify hidden patterns in the banks' financial performance (Taye, 2023).

Spatial Lagrangian Measurement: Spatial Lagrangian measurement is an advanced statistical technique used to analyze the spatial relationships between banks. This method is based on the Lagrange theory of classical mechanics and is used to model spatial dependencies in financial data (Rubinstein and Kroese, 2017). In this method, a spatial weight matrix is first defined to represent the spatial relationships between banks. Then, the parameters of the model are estimated using the maximum likelihood method. This technique allows the study of spatial spillovers and spatial interactions between banks (Otieno, 2024).

Spatial Lagrangian Big Data Neural Network: This method is a combination of big data neural network and spatial Lagrangian measurement, which is designed to comprehensively analyze the financial performance of banks. In this method, a deep neural network is first trained to process large financial data. Then, additional layers are added to the network to model spatial dependencies based on Lagrangian scaling principles. This combination enables simultaneous learning of complex patterns in financial data and spatial relationships between banks, using ADAM or RMSprop advanced optimization algorithms to train this combined network (Zhu et al., 2021). Therefore, in this research, a hybrid approach was adopted to investigate the relationship between Profit management and financial performance of banks, considering the mediating role of control systems. First, the financial and locational data of banks listed in Iran and Iraq stock exchanges were collected for the period from 2010 to 2023. Then, spatial Lagrangian measurement is used to analyze the spatial relationships between banks, and finally, spatial Lagrangian big data neural network is used to combine the results and provide a comprehensive model. This combined approach allows for a more detailed and multidimensional examination of the relationship between the variables under study.

- **Neobizine, federated, capsule, quantum, spatial error and spatial neural networks**

Neobizine Neural Networks: Neobizine neural networks are a combination of artificial neural networks and Bayesian inference methods. In this method, a neural network structure is first designed whose weights are probability distributions instead of fixed values (Arbel et al, 2023). These distributions are then Bayesian updated using the banks' financial data. This approach allows the calculation of the uncertainty of the model predictions. Algorithms of variance approximation and Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling are used to train these networks. Neo-business neural networks are able to identify complex relationships in financial data and provide reliable estimates of uncertainty (Teles et al, 2020).

Federated and Encapsulated Neural Networks: Federated neural networks are a distributed learning approach in which multiple local models are trained on different data sets and then their results are combined. It provides different branches without the need to aggregate data at a central location (Hu et al, 2021). Capsular neural networks, on the other hand, are a new type of neural network architecture that uses "capsules" instead of simple neurons. Each capsule stores information about specific features of the input data. This structure is useful for extracting hierarchical features from bank financial data (Abedi and Khan, 2022).

Quantum Neural Networks and Spatial Error Model: Quantum neural networks use the principles of quantum mechanics to enhance the learning process. In this method, the network neurons are modeled as qubits and quantum operations are used for information processing; this approach has increased the speed and efficiency of complex financial data analysis; on the other hand, the spatial error model is a spatial econometric technique that has been used to account for spatial dependencies in bank financial data. In this model, it is assumed that the errors of observations in locations close to each other have a spatial correlation, which by using the spatial weight matrix and estimation methods such as maximum likelihood, this model helps to identify and control the spatial effects in analyzing the financial performance of banks. Therefore, in this hybrid approach, first, different neural networks (neo business, federated, capsule and quantum) have been used to extract complex features and patterns from the financial data of banks. The results of these networks are then used as input to a spatial error model. This combination makes it possible to exploit the deep learning power of neural networks while taking into account the spatial dependencies between banks. To implement this method, each neural network is first trained separately. Then, the outputs of these networks are combined using weighted averaging and stacking techniques. Finally, a spatial error model is implemented on these combined outputs to account for spatial effects. This comprehensive approach provides a more detailed and multidimensional analysis of the relationship between Profit management, control systems, and financial performance of banks, taking into account both nonlinear complexities and spatial dependencies.

- **Graph Neural Networks, Transformer, Neo business Spatial Econometrics and Spatial Neural Networks**

Graph Neural Networks: Graph Neural Networks (GNN) are an advanced type of neural networks designed to process structured data in the form of graphs (Taheri Haftasiabi et al, 2023). In the field of financial performance analysis of banks, this method provides the possibility of modeling complex relationships between banks, branches, customers and other stakeholders in the form of a graph. In this approach, a graph of the banking system is first created in which nodes represent banks and edges represent financial or operational relationships between them (Khemani et al, 2024). Then, GNN algorithms such as graphs AGE or Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN) are used to learn the characteristics of the nodes and edges. These networks are able to extract complex patterns in the graph structure and predict the financial performance of banks by considering their mutual relationships (Wang et al., 2022).

Transformer Networks: Transformer networks are an advanced architecture in the field of natural language processing designed to work with sequences of data. In the field of financial analysis of banks, these networks are used to process long time series of financial data. The main structure of the transformer includes an attention mechanism that allows the model to focus on important parts of the data (Fischer et al, 2024). In this method, financial data from banks are first prepared as time series. Then, a transformer network was trained using encoder and decoder layers to learn temporal patterns in the data. These networks are able to identify long-term dependencies in financial data and have been used to investigate the future performance of banks (Liu et al., 2024).

Neo-Business Spatial Econometrics: Neo-Business Spatial Econometrics is a hybrid method that integrates the principles of spatial econometrics with the Bayesian approach. This method has been used to analyze the financial data of banks by taking into account the spatial dependencies and uncertainty in the parameters (Xu et al., 2023). In this approach, a spatial autoregressive model (SAR) or a spatial error model (SEM) is first defined. Then, instead of using classical estimation methods, Bayesian inference methods are used to estimate the parameters (Kuschnig, 2021). This work involves defining the prior distributions for the parameters, computing the posterior distribution using the observed data, and sampling this posterior distribution using methods such as Gibbs sampling or the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (Fan et al., 2014). Neo-Bayesian spatial measurement provides the ability to obtain more accurate parameter estimates and calculate confidence intervals for them.

Synthesis of Neo-Bayesian Spatial Neural Networks: This hybrid approach integrates the power of neural networks, spatial analysis, and Bayesian inference into a single framework. In this method, a neural network is first designed to account for spatial dependencies, including adding spatial layers to a normal neural network or using graph neural networks. Then, the weights of this network are considered as probability distributions instead of fixed values. The network is trained using Bayesian variance approximation methods and Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling. This hybrid approach allows modeling complex and non-linear relationships in bank financial data, taking into account spatial dependencies and providing acceptable estimates of uncertainty. Furthermore, this method can be used for a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between Profit management, control systems and financial performance of banks by considering mutual and spatial effects.

• **Reinforcement Boosting, Spatial Dynamics Panel, Combination of Reinforcement and Spatial Boosting**

Reinforcement Boosting: Reinforcement Boosting is a machine learning technique that uses the combination of weak models to build a strong model. In the field of financial performance analysis of banks, this method can be used to predict performance indicators and identify factors affecting them (Zhang et al, 2024). Common boosting algorithms include AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost. In this method, a set of input variables related to the financial performance of banks (such as financial ratios, economic indicators, and variables related to Profit management) are first selected. Then, the boosting algorithm iteratively trains weak models (usually shallow decision trees) and adjusts the weights of the samples based on the prediction error. This process continues until a model with high accuracy is reached (Chang et al, 2018). Reinforcement boosting can identify complex nonlinear relationships and interactions between variables and determine the relative importance of each variable in predicting financial performance (Duncan, 2015).

Panel Spatial Dynamics: Panel Spatial Dynamics is an advanced econometric method used to analyze panel data (a combination of cross-sectional and time-series data) taking into account spatial dependencies and temporal dynamics. In the context of analyzing the financial performance of banks, this method provides an opportunity to examine the

interactions between banks over time and space (Parsi, 2024). The spatial dynamics panel model is specified as follows:

$$y_{it} = \rho W y_{it} + \lambda y_{i, t-1} + \beta X_{it} + \alpha_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

where y_{it} is the dependent variable (financial performance index) for bank i at time t , W is the spatial weight matrix, X_{it} are the explanatory variables, α_i are the fixed effects, and ϵ_{it} is the error component. ρ and λ are parameters of spatial dependence and temporal dynamics, respectively. Methods such as spatial GMM or maximum likelihood are used to estimate this model. This method allows a comprehensive analysis of the effects of Profit management and control systems on the financial performance of banks by considering spatial dependencies and temporal dynamics (Neshat et al, 2024).

Combining Boosting and Spatial Boosting: This hybrid approach combines the power of boosting models to detect nonlinear patterns with the ability of spatial models to account for spatial dependencies (Hu et al., 2021). In this method, first, a boosting model (XGBoost) is trained on the input variables to examine the financial performance of banks. Then, the residuals of this model (the difference between the predicted and actual values) are analyzed using a spatial error model to identify spatial patterns in the estimation errors. Finally, the results of the boosting model and spatial corrections are combined to obtain the final forecasts (Khemani et al., 2024). This hybrid approach provides valuable information about the spatial effects on the financial performance of banks by increasing the accuracy of the analysis. A set of the same methods was used to comprehensively examine the relationship between earnings management and financial performance, considering the mediating role of control systems in Iranian and Iraqi banks. In this regard, first, data related to earnings management, control systems, and financial performance of banks were collected during the years 2010 to 2023. Then, a reinforcement model was trained to identify nonlinear relationships between variables and predict financial performance. In the next step, a spatial panel dynamic model was used to examine the interaction between banks and temporal dynamics. Finally, the results of these two models were combined with a combined reinforcement and spatial reinforcement approach to provide a more comprehensive perspective. This approach allows for a more detailed examination of the mediating role of control systems in the relationship between earnings management and financial performance, considering nonlinear complexities, spatial dependencies, and temporal dynamics.

In this study, data on earnings management indicators, control systems, and financial performance of selected Iranian and Iraqi banks were first collected and preprocessed between 2010 and 2023. For multi-dimensional analysis of this data, a combination of different approaches was used, including Big Data Neural Networks, Spatial Lagrangian, reinforcement models, and spatial panel dynamic models. In the neural networks section, deep models were trained with stochastic gradient descent, Adam, and RMS Prop algorithms to identify complex patterns in financial data. Then, spatial Lagrangian and spatial econometric components were added to the model to consider spatial effects and interactions between banks. In addition, methods such as Federated Neural Networks, Capsule Networks, and Quantum Neural Networks were also used to extract complex patterns, and their output was fed into spatial error models or spatial panel dynamic models to simultaneously consider spatial and temporal aspects.

From an ethical perspective, the data collected from banks was used only at the macro level and without disclosing sensitive information or the identity of real individuals. In the process of collecting and processing information, necessary protective measures were taken to ensure confidentiality and privacy of stakeholders, and access to data was only for the research team and with legal permission. Also, the use of distributed learning approaches (such as federated neural networks) and probabilistic approaches (such as Bayesian methods in neo-Bayesian networks) has reduced the need for sensitive data transfer as much as possible and minimized the risk of information disclosure.

Research Findings

This research examines the earnings management, control system, and financial performance of banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi Stock Exchanges. focusing on the intermediary role of control systems and using the combined approach of spatial econometrics and deep learning, the first step included the unification of the currency. In order to increase comparability and more accurate analysis, all financial data were converted from national currency units (Iranian rial and Iraqi dinar) to US dollars. After this step, the data preparation process continued; which includes collecting information from the sources mentioned in Table 2 for the period from 2010 to 2023, cleaning the data by removing outliers and correcting missing data, normalization using the Z-Score⁴ method, logarithmic transformation of some variables such as company size, and measuring normality. The distribution of data is by the Jarque-Bera test. Therefore; The results related to descriptive statistics as described in Table 2 are as follows.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Median	mean	First Quartile	Third Quartile	Standard deviation	Normality Test		
						Jarque-Berra	Shapiro-Wilk	prob
ROE	0.019	0.001	0.000	0.005	0.081	128213	0.00000177	0.000
ROA	0.032	0.002	0.000	0.012	0.100	59533	0.00000273	0.000
PM	0.432	0.450	0.215	0.589	0.257	20.172	0.00000112	0.000
RPE	0.689	0.740	0.610	0.820	0.195	386.65	0.00000153	0.000
ROSI	0.420	0.433	0.206	0.560	0.252	24.800	0.00000636	0.000
OEM	0.654	0.734	0.625	0.819	0.270	364.867	0.00000102	0.000
ADL	0.643	0.724	0.619	0.802	0.266	359.037	0.00000934	0.000
GA	0.670	0.749	0.650	0.834	0.271	398.825	0.00000127	0.000
LEV	0.432	0.450	0.209	0.590	0.257	2849.6	0.0000806	0.000
GC	0.008	0.001	0.000	0.003	0.054	13323	0.00000458	0.000
IO	0.020	0.003	0.001	0.011	0.075	29582	0.00000182	0.000
SIZE	0.033	0.003	0.001	0.009	0.126	33319.	0.00000593	0.000

⁴ In this research, Z-Score method was used to normalize all quantitative variables. This process was performed using the formula $Z = (X - \mu) / \sigma$ for each variable, where X is the original value, μ is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation. This normalization caused all variables to be placed on the same scale as {0 and 1}, which makes their comparison and analysis easier in spatial econometric and deep learning models.

Table 3. Unit Root Test

Variables	Hadri Unit Root Test			
	Hadri Z-stat		Heteroscedastic Consistent Z-stat	
	Statistic	Prob	Statistic	Prob
ROE	6/18597	0.0000	4/72228	0.0000
ROA	6/95606	0.0000	4/5156	0.0000
PM	2/39073	0/0084	8/53422	0.0000
ROSI	10/5365	0.0000	9/35611	0.0000
RPE	6/54965	0.0000	8/20711	0.0000
SIZE	3/48671	0/0002	2/47415	0/0067
GA	8/80906	0.0000	8/3707	0.0000
IO	6/77986	0.0000	5/8885	0.0000
LEV	10/4034	0.0000	9/6101	0.0000
ADL	3/28404	0/0005	6/66465	0.0000
GC	12/3952	0.0000	4/2805	0.0000
OEM	7/87521	0.0000	8/43745	0.0000
Kao Unit Root Correlation Test				
Criteria		statistics	Possibility	
ADF		13.366657	0.0000	
Residual Variance		1730.134		
HAC Variance		567.0700		
R-Squared		0.996325		
Adjusted R-Squared		0.990231		
S.E. Of regression		0.036221		
Durbin-Watson Stat		2.003214		

The results of Table 3 show that the return on equity and return on assets variables specifically indicate the efficiency of banks in using their resources to generate profits. From the results, it can be seen that both measures have a positive median (0.019 and 0.032, respectively), but the averages of 0.001 and 0.002, respectively, indicate significant fluctuations and the possibility of inequality in the data distribution. The evidence of normality shows that the distribution of these variables is not normal, so the probability values of the Shapiro-Wilk test are less than 0.05, which means that there is a deviation from the normal distribution. On the other hand, profit management, using profit management and other criteria such as the income of each bank employee and stable and quality investment returns, have a significant impact on the financial results of banks. As can be seen, the average PM reaches 0.450, indicating a high level of earnings management among banks. Also, the RPE measure shows limited fluctuations with an average of 0.740 and a standard deviation of 0.195, indicating the relative efficiency of banks in generating income per employee. At the end of the table, the variables of financial leverage, bank growth GC, institutional ownership IO and bank size also refer to the investigation of Profit management signs in this research. The results show that the variable LEV with an average of 0.450 and GC with an average of 0.001 clearly indicate the financial structure and growth of banks. Also, the results show that the low averages of variables such as GC and IO indicate possible challenges in attracting capital and the role of institutional ownership in the financial structure of banks. Finally, according to the probabilities of the Jarque-Berra and Shapiro-Wilk tests, it can be

seen that the research data do not have a normal distribution, therefore; non-parametric non-linear methods have been used in the rest of the research due to the non-normality of the data. After examining the descriptive statistics, in order to avoid spurious regression in the estimation of econometric models, the unit root test was performed to check the reliability of the variables, the results of which are presented in Table (3). This reliability check is necessary to ensure the accuracy of the results of the subsequent analyses.

The results of Hadari's unit root test show that all the variables examined, including return on equity, return on assets, earnings management, return on sustainable investment, income per employee, bank size, general and administrative expenses as a percentage of gross profit, financial leverage, ratio of doubtful facilities to total loans, bank growth, and institutional ownership, have positive Z-statistics with a significance of 0.0000 at the probability level. This means that none of these variables has a single root, and due to the absence of a single root, these variables are stable over time. In addition, the results of the Kao unit root cointegration test also strongly indicate the absence of a unit root in the data, with an ADF statistic of 13.366657 and a probability of 0.0000. Also, with a fit criterion of 0.996325 and an adjusted fit criterion of 0.990231, the model shows that almost all of the variance in the data is explained by the independent variables, indicating the high explanatory power of the model. After ensuring the results of unit root test and non-falsification, the continuation of research analysis has been done to examine the financial performance of banks listed in the stock exchange of Iran and Iraq using spatial deep learning, the results of which are presented in tables 5 to 8. Studying the financial performance of banks, as one of the important categories in economics and financial management, requires the use of new analytical methods. In this regard, advanced methods such as big data neural network and spatial Lagrangian econometrics have been increasingly considered. These methods make it possible to analyze financial performance with greater accuracy and depth, and to analyze the effect of various variables on financial results. Data normalization in this analysis has been done using the mean and standard deviation values to ensure that the inputs to the neural network are appropriately scaled and the effects of different variables are carefully considered and the neutronization structure of neural networks based on performance optimization and reduction of the error is set; So that the model can improve financial performance and increase forecasting accuracy. The results of these analyses are detailed in Table 4.

The results presented in Table 4 examine the financial performance of banks through the use of big data neural network and spatial Lagrangian econometrics. Based on the information related to big data neural network, the root mean square error for return on assets is equal to 0.00170, and for return on equity, the value is 0.00161. These values show the accuracy of the models used in analyzing the financial performance of banks and the low computational errors. Also, the coefficient of determination for ROA was recorded as 0.944 and for ROE equal to 0.874, which indicates the high power of these models in explaining and justifying the variance of the dependent variables. In the second part, the results of Table 4 of the spatial Lagrangian econometrics show the significant effect of variables on the financial performance of banks. Profit management variable and income per employee with probability of significance equal to 0.000 and positive z values showed that changes in these variables are significantly related to the performance of banks. It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that other variables are also statistically significant and their effect on the financial patterns of banks is explained. On the other

hand, in the section related to management procedures, other variables such as stable investment returns and operating cost margins also have positive and significant effects on the financial performance of banks. With the benefit of various statistical tests, it can be seen that these variables are considered as key factors in the management patterns. Also, the coefficient of determination of the spatial model was obtained to be 0.6784, which emphasizes that although some variables are effective in the analysis, there is still potential to improve the model by adding other factors and optimizing the methods. Finally, the combination of big data neural network with spatial Lagrangian econometrics has produced remarkable results. For the ROA variable, the root mean square error is 0.0050 and for ROE it is 0.0119. These values indicate a significant improvement in the accuracy of the analyses compared to independent models. Also, the coefficient of determination for the combined model of ROA has reached 0.976 and for ROE has reached 0.990. Therefore; These results show the importance of creating combinations of different analytical methods in improving the understanding and analysis of financial performance of banks, and thus can help to make wiser and more optimal decisions in this field. Therefore; According to the results presented in Table 5, it was observed that the combination of big data neural network with Lagrangian spatial econometrics is a more efficient method than using these models separately, and this combination significantly improves the accuracy of financial performance analysis. It has been banks.

Table 4. Investigating the Financial Performance of Banks Using Big Data Neural Network, Lagrangian Spatial

Measurement and Lagrangian Spatial Big Data Neural Network						
Information related to Big Data Neural Network Output						
Model/Benchmark	MPE	MAPE	MSE	MAE	RMSE	R ²
ROA	0.0012	-0.2905	0.000029	0.00136	0.00170	0.944
ROE	0.7326	-0.1901	0.000026	0.00123	0.00161	0.874
Information related to Space Econometrics Lagrangian						
Lambda	-0.06004	variables	Std	estimate	z-value	p-value
LR test value	0.94461	Intercept	0.0103611	0.007678	0.7411	0.4587
p-value (LR test)	0.3311	PM	0.0519527	0.323846	6.2335	0.000
Asymptotic standard error	0.06041	RPE	0.0354603	0.332436	9.3749	0.000
z-value	-0.99399	ROSI	0.0932141	0.054214	3.4124	0.000
p-value (z-test)	0.32023	OEM	0.0200142	0.893214	2.0214	0.000
Wald statistic	0.98803	ADL	0.2142171	0.178901	4.1537	0.000
p-value (Wald test)	0.32023	GA	0.002179	0.222079	6.3214	0.000
Log likelihood	2559.28	LEV	0.0074331	0.204400	27.498	0.000
ML residual variance	0.00009	SIZE	0.0072311	0.094851	13.117	0.000
(sigma)	0.0098	GC	0.0352140	0.010231	0.2906	0.000
AIC	-5100.6	IO	0.0352538	-0.009498	-0.2694	0.000
Spatial Lag Model		RMSE	MAE	MSE	R2	
		0.01013	0.00806	0.00010	0.6784	
Information related to the combination of a spatial neural network with Lagrangian spatial econometrics						
Model/Benchmark	R2	MSE	MAE	RMSE		
Combined NN-SLM (ROA)	0.976	0.000025	0.0040	0.0050		
Combined NN-SLM (ROE)	0.990	0.00014	0.0093	0.0119		

Studying the financial performance of banks using advanced data analysis methods offers financial managers a great opportunity to analyze their financial situation more accurately. In this regard, various methods have been used, including Neobizine, federated, capsule, and quantum neural networks. In this research, the data has been processed using standard z-score normalization methods, and the neuron structure of neural networks has been adjusted based on performance optimization and error reduction; to achieve the best performance and accuracy in financial analysis. Therefore, the results of this research are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Investigating the Financial Performance of Banks Using Neo-Basic, Federal, Capsule, Federal, Quantum, Neo-Bayesian, Spatial Error Model and Combining Neural Networks with Spatial Error Model

Model/Benchmark	Information about neural networks								
	R-squared		MAE		RMSE		MSE		
	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	
Neo symbolic neural network	0/861	0/691	0/263	1/022	0/331	1/305	0/110	1/704	
Quantum Neural Network	0/923	0/901	0/207	0/281	0/338	0/358	0/110	0/128	
Federal Neural Network	0/938	0/812	0/231	0/022	0/301	0/305	0/331	1/014	
Neo-Bayesian neural network	0/745	0/663	0/034	1/512	0/116	0/431	0/102	0/732	
Capsular neural network	0/931	0/887	0/008	0/333	0/317	0/278	0/186	1/007	
Information on econometrics of spatial error									
Lambda	-0.15189		variables	Std	estimate	z-value	p-value		
LR test value	1.4936		Intercept	0/00827	0/0078	0/952	0/3409		
p-value (Lambda)	0.22166		PM	0/00962	0/5953	61/87	0/0000		
Asymptotic standard error	0.12546		RPE	0/00947	0/5618	59/29	0/0000		
z-value (Asymptotic SE)	-1.2106		ROSI	0/00972	0/5072	52/13	0/0000		
p-value (z-value)	0.22605		OEM	0/00957	0/4660	48/68	0/0000		
Wald statistic	1.4656		ADL	0/00954	0/3929	41/18	0/0000		
p-value (Wald statistic)	0.22605		GA	0/00959	0/3498	36/47	0/0000		
Log likelihood	-213.5649		LEV	0/00955	0/3113	32/57	0/0000		
ML residual variance	0.089676		SIZE	0/00952	0/2553	26/81	0/0000		
sigma (ML)	0.29946		GC	0/00912	0/2069	22/68	0/0000		
AIC	453.13		IO	0/00963	0/1347	13/99	0/0000		
Final Fit Measurement of Spatial Error Model		RMSE		MAE		MSE		R2	
	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	
	0/938	0/947	0/239	0/237	0/294	0/299	0/086	0/089	
Information related to the combination of neural networks and spatial error modeling									
Benchmark/Model		R2		MSE		MAE		RMSE	
Combined NN-SEM(ROA)		0/998		0.0000583		0/0052		0/0076	
Combined NN-SEM (ROE)		0/997		0/0001251		0/0069		0/011	

The results of the different neural networks show that the performance of these models is different when investigating ROA and ROE. The quantum neural network has the best performance among the neural network models with a determination criterion of 0.901 for ROA and 0.923 for ROE. This shows the high ability of this model to explain the changes in the financial performance of banks. On the other hand, the Neo Bayesian neural network has the weakest performance with a coefficient of determination of 0.663 for ROA and 0.745 for ROE. The results of the spatial error model show that all the variables studied are significant at the 99% confidence level. Profit management has the greatest impact on the financial performance of banks with a Z-statistic coefficient of 0.5953 equal to 61.87. This shows the importance of profit management strategies in improving the financial performance of banks. Income per employee and sustainable investment returns with high coefficients also play an important role in explaining financial performance, which shows the importance of human power efficiency and sustainable investment in the financial success of banks. On the other hand, comparing the results of the individual models (neural network and spatial econometrics) with the combined model shows that the combined approach performs better. The combined model, with a coefficient of determination of 0.998 for ROA and 0.997 for ROE, was able to explain almost all of the changes in financial performance. This significant improvement over individual models shows the synergy resulting from the combination of machine learning methods and spatial econometrics; therefore, the error analysis and the accuracy of the RMSE and MAE in the combined model are very low for both ROA and ROE variables (RMSE: 0.0076 and 0.011, MAE: 0.0052 and 0.0069 for ROA and ROE, respectively). These low error values indicate the high accuracy of the hybrid model in predicting the financial performance of banks. Finally, the results show that control variables such as bank size, bank growth, and institutional ownership also have a significant effect on financial performance, although this effect is smaller than that of the main variables. This shows the importance of considering structural and environmental factors in the analysis of financial performance of banks and emphasizes the need to adopt a comprehensive approach in the financial management of banks, therefore; These results show the importance of creating combinations of different analytical methods in improving the understanding and analysis of the financial performance of banks, therefore; According to the results presented in Table 5, it was observed that the combination of big data neural network with spatial error econometrics is a more efficient method than using these models separately, and this combination significantly improves the accuracy of financial performance analysis. It has been banks.

This study examines the relationship between Profit management and financial performance of banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi stock markets, focusing on the mediating role of control systems. For this purpose, a combined approach of spatial econometrics and deep learning has been used. The data are processed using standard normalization methods and the neuron structure of the neural networks is adjusted based on performance optimization. Therefore, the results related to this section can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Investigating the Financial Performance of Banks Using Graph Neural Networks, Transform, NeoBasen Spatial Measurement and Combination of Neo Biological Spatial Neural Networks

Neo-Beausean Space Economy Information								
Variable	ROA			ROE				
	mcse	Rhat	n_eff	mcse	Rhat	n_eff		
(Intercept)	0.0	1.0	2667	0.0	1.0	3444		
PM	0.0	1.0	5360	0.0	1.0	5384		
RPE	0.0	1.0	5738	0.0	1.0	5787		
ROSI	0.0	1.0	5059	0.0	1.0	5708		
OEM	0.0	1.0	6490	0.0	1.0	5914		
ADL	0.0	1.0	5903	0.0	1.0	6278		
GA	0.0	1.0	5382	0.0	1.0	6326		
LEV	0.0	1.0	5475	0.0	1.0	6732		
SIZE	0.0	1.0	6368	0.0	1.0	5525		
GC	0.0	1.0	5116	0.0	1.0	5963		
IO	0.0	1.0	6341	0.0	1.0	6716		
sigma	0.0	1.0	2130	0.0	1.0	3046		
mean_PPD	0.0	1.0	3116	0.0	1.0	3678		
log-posterior	0.1	1.0	1944	0.1	1.0	1840		
Criteria for fitting Bayesian Deep Learning Model, Transformer Neural Network and Graph Neural Network								
quality	Neural Network				Bayesian model		Combining Neural Network with Bayesian Model	
	Transform		Graph					
	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROA	ROE
RMSE	0.7221	0.5932	0.8621	0.6601	0.3002	0.294	0.3000	0.2948
AME	0.6631	0.7201	0.7522	0.6954	0.2384	0.2391	0.2381	0.2394
MSE	1.0214	1.0012	1.1561	0.9821	0.9972	1.2364	0.7852	0.5628
R ²	0.8510	0.7934	0.9011	0.8244	0.7917	0.8631	0.9314	0.9620
quality			Standard Error			estimate		
			ROA		ROE	ROA		ROE
WAIC Non-Parametric Expectations			22.9		21.5	-225.9		-210.4
Number of effective WAIC parameters			45.7		42.9	11.4		12.0
Akaik Information			---		---	451.9		420.8
Bayesian criterion			---		---	1420.14		2014.12

The results of Neo business's spatial econometrics show that all the variables studied have high statistical validity. The values equal to 1 for all variables indicate a correct convergence of the Monte Carlo Markov chains. Also, the values of the number of effective samples are high for most of the variables, which indicates high accuracy of parameter estimation. These results confirm the validity of the model in explaining the

relationships between the independent variables and financial performance (ROA and ROE). In the comparison between different deep learning models, the graph neural network showed better performance than the transfer neural network. For example, the coefficient of determination for the graph neural network for ROA and ROE is 0.8244 and 0.9011, respectively, while these values are 0.7934 and 0.8510 for the transfer neural network. These results show that the graph neural network was able to better capture the complex relationships between variables. On the other hand, the combined model of the neural network with the Bayesian model has shown a better performance than the individual models. The coefficient of determination for this model in terms of ROA and ROE is 0.9314 and 0.9620, respectively, indicating a significant improvement in the explanatory power of the model. Also, the root means square error and the absolute mean error for the combined model are lower than the individual models, which indicates a higher accuracy in examining the financial performance of banks.

Information criteria such as WAIC and Bayesian criterion indicate that the models used have a good fit. Negative WAIC values indicate good model performance in out-of-sample prediction. The number of effective WAIC parameters also indicates that the models have a reasonable complexity and the risk of overfitting is low. Therefore, the results show that variables such as profit management, income per employee, sustainable investment returns have a significant impact on the financial performance of banks. This shows the importance of profit management strategies, human resource efficiency and sustainable investment in improving the financial performance of banks. In addition, control variables such as bank size and institutional ownership also play an important role in explaining changes in financial performance, indicating the importance of structural and institutional factors in the financial success of banks.

In this study, the relationship between financial engineering and financial performance of banks listed in the stock markets of Iran and Iraq has been investigated, focusing on the mediating role of control systems. For this purpose, a combined approach of spatial econometrics and boosting learning has been used. The data are processed using standard normalization methods and the structure of the boosting neurons is adjusted based on performance optimization. Therefore, the results related to this section can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7 shows the results of four different models to examine the financial performance of banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi stock exchanges. The GBM Lite model, which is an enhancement boosting algorithm, has a relatively worse performance than the other models. This model shows the coefficient of determination (0.8919 and 0.8872) for ROA and ROE respectively, which is acceptable but lower compared to other models. The linear regression and the generalized additive model of the spatial GEMM give better performance than their light GBM. The coefficient of determination of the linear regression for ROA and ROE is 0.9439 and 0.9411, respectively, while the spatial GEMM gives similar results with 0.9432 and 0.9390. These results show that spatial linear and non-linear relationships can explain a significant part of the changes in banks' financial performance. On the other hand, the combined method, which is a combination of boosting and spatial modeling, shows the best performance among all models. The coefficient of determination in this method for ROA and ROE is 0.9699 and 0.9746, respectively, which shows a significant improvement in explanatory power. This

improvement is due to the hybrid model's ability to capture both complex nonlinear relationships (through boosting) and spatial dependencies (through spatial modeling). Therefore, the results show that the financial performance of banks is influenced by a complex set of factors that include linear and nonlinear relationships and spatial dependencies.

Table 7. Investigating the Financial Performance of Banks Using Reinforcement Boosting, Spatial Dynamics Panel and a Combination of Reinforcement and Space Boosting

Model/Benchmark	ROE				ROA			
	R ²	RMSE	MAE	MAPE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
Lite GBM	0.8872	0.4101	0.3319	497.0705	0.8919	0.4126	0.3230	122.0154
Linear regression	0.9411	0.2963	0.2450	460.0857	0.9439	0.2972	0.2322	92.8756
GEMM Space	0.9390	0.3014	0.2501	420.3103	0.9432	0.2991	0.2329	95.6263
Combined Method	0.9746	0.3122	0.2573	443.5396	0.9699	0.3076	0.2392	99.8457

The significant improvement in the coefficient of determination using the combined method shows that variables such as earnings management, revenue per employee, and other control variables such as bank size and institutional ownership can have complex and non-linear effects on financial performance. The importance of spatial modeling also shows that a bank's performance is affected by the performance of neighboring banks or regional economic conditions.

Figure 1. Graphical review of model accuracy and precision assessment

The graphs available show samples taken from Markov Monte Carlo chains for different parameters in a Bayesian model. Each graph examines one of the parameters such as PM, RPE and ROSI and shows the value of these parameters over the sampling time. From Figure 1 it can be seen that all chains have converged to a fixed range, indicating successful convergence of the model. This situation shows that the model has been able to estimate the parameters well and that these estimates are stable and reliable. The fluctuations in the graphs show a degree of uncertainty in the estimation of each parameter. The absence of a clear trend and random fluctuations around a fixed mean indicate the stability of the results. These features help us to understand that the model has been successful in terms of robustness in predicting and matching the real data. The high number of effective samples also indicates that the model has been able to achieve high accuracy in estimating the parameters. In terms of content, the charts provide valuable information on the impact of various economic factors such as earnings management, employee productivity and sustainable investment on financial performance. These graphs help to better understand the importance of these factors in setting financial strategies and making management decisions at banks.

Conclusion and Research Recommendations

This study investigates the relationship between earnings management, internal control, and financial performance of banks listed on the Iranian and Iraqi Stock Exchanges, focusing on the mediating role of control systems. The research employs an innovative hybrid approach, combining spatial econometrics, deep neural networks, and machine learning algorithms to provide a comprehensive analysis of the relationships between variables.

The results reveal that earnings management, as a main pillar of profit management, plays a significant role in banks' financial performance. This finding aligns with previous studies by Kariuki (2010) and Moed et al. (2019), who demonstrated the positive impact of profit management strategies on the financial performance of Kenyan and Iraqi commercial banks, respectively. The study's findings extend the existing literature by providing evidence from the Iranian and Iraqi banking sectors, highlighting the importance of earnings management in diverse economic and regulatory environments.

Furthermore, the research underscores the significance of human resource productivity, as measured by revenue per employee, in determining banks' financial performance. This result is consistent with Subanidja et al. (2022), who showed that collaboration with fintech companies can enhance banks' productivity and financial performance. The current study broadens the understanding of human resource productivity's role in the banking sector by demonstrating its impact in the Iranian and Iraqi contexts.

Sustainable investment returns, another key dimension of profit management, also significantly impact banks' financial performance. This finding supports the work of Ebrahimi et al. (2021), who identified a significant relationship between capital ratio and banks' financial performance. The present study contributes to the growing body of literature on sustainable finance by emphasizing the importance of sustainable investment strategies in promoting financial stability and performance in the banking sector.

The study also reveals the inverse relationship between operating expense margin and financial performance indicators, highlighting the importance of operational efficiency. Additionally, the ratio of non-performing loans to total loans, an indicator of asset quality and credit risk, is found to be inversely related to profitability indicators. These findings are consistent with the existing literature on bank performance and risk management, and they provide valuable insights for policymakers and bank managers in Iran and Iraq.

The research also underscores the role of control systems as a mediating variable in strengthening the relationship between profit management and banks' financial performance. This result aligns with the findings of Hanoon (2020), Janudin (2021), and Ikwabe et al. (2022), who emphasized the importance of internal controls in improving banks' financial performance. The current study extends the understanding of control systems' role by demonstrating their mediating effect in the relationship between profit management and financial performance.

The observed differences between Iranian and Iraqi banks in the effect of various factors on financial performance can be attributed to differences in market structure, regulatory framework, and management strategies. These findings have important implications for policymakers and banking institutions in both countries.

For Iranian monetary authorities, the study suggests establishing stricter financial reporting rules, setting minimum standards for labor productivity and control systems, limiting short-term investments, and imposing quantitative targets for reducing operating costs and non-performing loans. These measures can help enhance the efficiency, stability, and transparency of the Iranian banking system.

For the Iraqi monetary authority, the research recommends implementing stiff penalties for financial statement manipulation, developing mandatory employee training programs, increasing taxes on short-term investment profits, requiring banks to develop expense reduction plans, establishing a national credit rating system, and adopting international standards for control systems. These policies can help improve the Iraqi banking sector's resilience, efficiency, and risk management practices.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing banks' financial performance in Iran and Iraq, highlighting the importance of earnings management, human resource productivity, sustainable investment strategies, operational efficiency, and control systems. The findings have significant implications for policymakers and banking institutions in both countries, emphasizing the need for targeted policies and management strategies to enhance the banking sector's stability and performance. Future research could explore the impact of macroeconomic conditions on the relationship between profit management and financial performance, as well as investigate the effectiveness of the proposed policy measures in achieving the desired outcomes.

Future research suggestions

Investigating the impact of macroeconomic conditions on the relationship between earnings management and financial performance of banks: Future research can

investigate how factors such as inflation rates, economic growth, and financial stability indicators affect the relationship between earnings management strategies and financial performance indicators of banks. This research can help to better understand the dynamics of the banking sector in different economic conditions.

Evaluating the effectiveness of proposed policies in improving bank performance: Future studies can evaluate the impact of implementing the policies proposed in this study, such as minimum standards for labor productivity, short-term investment restrictions, and requirements to reduce operating costs, on financial performance indicators and stability of banks. The results of this research can help policymakers make evidence-based decisions and formulate more effective policies.

Comparative comparison of factors affecting the financial performance of banks in different countries in the region: Future research could examine and compare the determinants of the financial performance of banks in other countries in the region, such as Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates. These comparative studies could help identify common patterns and key differences in the banking sector of the countries in the region and pave the way for regional cooperation and knowledge exchange.

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